

Fostering Solidarity and Fraternity in Indian Context

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Abstract

This article is an attempt to learn from the recent encyclical ‘Fratelli Tutti’ some concrete practices that would help us make the wisdom of the document visible in our Indian soil. We try to be the leaven of friendship and solidarity in our mother country. The author suggests five steps through which this could be achieved. The assertion that we are the children of the soil who by informed choice have chosen to follow Christ and the place of the birth of Christianity has nothing to do with it is emphasized. Then the call to walk with all the people of our land regardless of the differences in faith-traditions is suggested. The life of the leaders of the church both the clergy and the religious need to integrate the practices of the saints of the church and the sages of India in their witnessing life. And finally, a call for an integrated holistic catechism and promotion of lay leadership in the secular roles of power is also thought of and presented.

Introduction

We are called to Respond to the invitation of Pope Francis in the encyclical ‘Fratelli Tutti’ to fashion a world encircled by social friendship and fraternity. How are we going to be the channel of fraternity and social friendship in our Indian soil? 1. The first way to make this possible is to get rooted in our multifaceted plurality of cultural riches. We all need to be deeply and rightfully convinced that our faith does not make us aliens in our mother land. The claim that the origin of a faith tradition must necessarily be rooted in Indian soil to have a true sense of belonging, is a malicious conspiracy of a few vested interest groups to politically mobilize a spuriously manufactured faith-based majority. Our belonging to Indianness in and through our cultural and linguistic specificities is a given, prior to the choice of faith practices. 2. Once we have the unquestionable assertion of our cultural roots, then we need to walk along with others. The journey of a Christian can never be alone. Regardless of the faith of our neighbours, we walk with them to create a world for all. 3. In this journey the leadership of the priests and religious plays an

important role and the evangelical counsels need to be tinged with the renunciatory living practices of the Indian sages of the past. 4. If we need to pass on this culture of solidarity and friendship, we need to school our younger generation with an integrated catechesis that flows to the world from the faith. 5. We are also committed to engage in promoting people of goodwill to assume the role in politics and governing structures.

Christians rooted in Indian soil

There is conspired and deliberate attempt to stereotype all the Christians in India to be aliens in the land. The narrative that Christians are antithetical to the interest of the nation's progress and they serve the agenda of their European and Western masters is gaining ground in Indian soil. The othering of Christians had been intentionally foisted to discredit the phenomenal contribution that they have made in the nation building. All the noble efforts to genuinely partake in the upliftment of millions of the fellow brothers and sisters of India is treacherously maligned and shamefully reduced to means to convert people to Christianity.¹ Perhaps, we need to seek pardon for the aberrations that might have happened in the vast land of India in the name of Christ. It is high time that we began to be assertive about our Indian identity. We are 'Indian Christians' and we are not the leftovers of the colonial past. We are Indians who have embraced the faith in Jesus Christ without compromising our cultural roots. We have been enriched by the Christian faith and Christian faith or church has been enriched by the diverse cultures. We cannot neglect the gift of the spirit that is dialoguing between our Indian cultures and the message of the gospel. We have willingly seeded the Christian faith in our Indian hearts. Our choice of faith in Christ did not stem from an inferior understanding or perception of the religions born in Indian soil. It is actually the typical characteristic of every Indian to seek the place of faith and worship that helps his spiritual journey to find union with the divine. Therefore, in embracing the gospel, we have actually behaved with true Indian spirit.

In this regard, given the current scenario, Christians need to be familiar with our stand and fight against the British during the freedom struggle.² Even though we shared the same faith with the colonizers, the quest for a free nation

¹ Evangeli Nuntiandi, no. 80. Conversion is not the goal of christianity

² Raka Mukherjee and Zoya Mateen, "A Note to The BJP Lawmaker Who Said Christians Didn't Help in Freedom Struggle: You're Wrong," *News 18 Buzz*, 06 July 2018, <https://www.news18.com/news/buzz/a-note-to-the-bjp-lawmaker-who-said-christians-didnt-help-in-freedom-struggle-youre-wrong-1803493.html> (accessed on 21 March 2021)

didn't fail to stir the hearts of Indian Christians. We owned the fight for freedom as every true Indian did at the time. We felt that fighting for one's liberty was intrinsically a Christian call (proclaim liberty to the captives) and every follower of Christ was duty-bound to participate in the struggle for emancipation. Raising our voices with fellow Indians, we actually manifested our Christian witness.³

Building Communities of People

It might appear natural that feathers of the same bird flock together. We might want ourselves to be closely connected to fellow believers of the same religion. It is true that our faith-expressions might demand that we come together to bear witness to the Christian vocation. Our unique differences as Christians are there to richly contribute and enhance the life in the diverse collective. We are part of the whole. We are a member of a larger Indian family. Wherever Christians are, people of other faith must feel welcome. They are not people with non-identity. We do not define them by who we are. They are not non-Christians. They bear their unique identity and faith.⁴ They may not want to share our spiritual or religious space with them. Still the joys and struggles of all human beings in their existential realm are similar. We need to collaborate with the other faithful. A famous quote attributed to Levinas says that food for me is my material need and food for my neighbor is my spiritual need. The material needs of my neighbour are my spiritual needs. We cannot parochially define our bonding and connections with sameness and uniformity. The differences in our religious or spiritual spaces need not deter us to form convergence in our efforts to establish justice at the secular spaces. Nevertheless, our struggles and needs are more common than we can imagine. We cannot be forming ghettos by restricting our living spaces to same groups. In the ghettos, the rupture for a furnace is simmering in the hiding.⁵ Indeed, “only the man who approaches others, not to draw them into his own life, but to help them become ever more fully themselves, can truly be called a father” (*Fratelli Tutti*, No. 4). “We want to be a Church that serves, that leaves home and goes forth from its places of

³ Joe Palathunkal, “Social amnesia buries India's Catholic freedom fighters”, UCA News, 16 August 2020, <https://www.ucanews.com/news/social-amnesia-buries-indias-catholic-freedom-fighters/89164#>

⁴ Doni Raja F., “‘We’ because of ‘they’: what Ubuntu spells,” *The Hindu*, 10 September 2017, <https://www.thehindu.com/opinion/open-page/we-because-of-they-what-ubuntu-spells/article19651234.ece> (accessed on 20 March 2021).

⁵ Mohsin Alam Bhat, “Bigotry At Home: How Delhi, Mumbai Keep Muslim Tenants Out”, *Article 14*, 11 February 2021, <https://www.article-14.com/post/bigotry-at-home-how-delhi-mumbai-keep-muslim-tenants-out> (accessed on 19 March 2021).

worship, goes forth from its sacristies, in order to accompany life, to sustain hope, to be the sign of unity... to build bridges, to break down walls, to sow seeds of reconciliation” (*Fratelli Tutti*, No. 276).

Pastors and Religious People

Pastors and religious people need to be men of outstanding virtue,⁶ following the simplicity and frugal path of the sages of the yester years. People who shepherd the faithful need to be persons of uncompromising faithfulness and holiness. Our land is not unfamiliar to the lives of sages and holy men and women. Our land since the ancient times have had so many spiritual seekers. Their life has always been characterized by frugality, austerity and asceticism. While emulating their path of simple living, we also need to willingly commit ourselves in the struggles and joys of the people of the land. Our journey is not an isolated journey but a collective journey. While we walk along with people, we must not forget the unique role of seekers with a Christian mark. We share both the apostolic poverty of the disciples and the frugality of the sage seekers. We cannot leave the sheepfold in the open wilderness and build palaces for ourselves in the secured walls. Whenever the sheep raise their heads, they need to see the affirming presence of the shepherd. For that, we need to share space with the sheep and be vigilant. Being Indian pastors and Indian religious demands that our poverty is both evangelical and material, our chastity relational and unquestionably above suspicion, our obedience institutional and charismatic.

Integrated catechesis

A formation that integrates faith with justice is essential for the Christians of India. Somehow, for too long, we have been mired in sustaining and reinforcing the social differences by birth especially by caste. This has always shown the life of Christian witness in poor light. We have been pharisaic and hypocritical in our relationship with fellow followers. Our catechesis, on the one hand, must help us deeply rooted in the gospel and on the other hand, help us critically question the taken-for-granted dimensions of social living and thereby re-commit ourselves to changing the traditional stratified societal behaviours and attitudes. Thus, we, guided by the Spirit of the lord, pave the way for a communal living conform to the reign of God that our lord practiced wherever he went. The sacred and the secular must be blended and mutually challenge each other to understand the truth of the gospel

⁶ M.K. George, “Stan in Jail: Implications for Christian Mission in India,” *Jivan*, December 2020 – January 2021, 19.

better. We can never exhaust the hidden secrets of the reign of God in the gospels. That is one of the reasons for its lasting freshness for centuries. It remains a light to us, the disciples of Christ. Our catechesis is not an exercise of mere knowledge accumulation of what and how the faith is contained in the dogmas, doctrines and creed but who we can become and how we can relate with others, nature and oneself. Our faith sustained through such catechesis will enable us to discern correctly our political discourse, social engagement and economic commitment. One that integrates the sacred and the secular: political consciousness with critical religious education.

Encouraging people of Good will to take up public responsibilities

Today, the legislative, the executive and the judiciary of the country is in disarray with a rarity of hope flickering sporadically. If we need to rediscover their original charism as envisioned by the founding fathers, we need many good people taking up these responsible roles. Those who have the talent and will but lack wherewithal to pursue a career in these places of power, need to be supported by the church. “People from the peripheries of life have another way of looking at things; they see aspects of reality that are invisible to the centers of power where weighty decisions are made” (*Fratelli Tutti*, No. 215). The church also needs to play a role beyond running and managing secondary and higher educational institutions. It needs to engage in running centers that facilitate the ordinary people to take up jobs from the lower rung to higher rung of the government services. This will bring in much needed systemic and structural cleansing of the corrupt systems and indifferent structures and enliven their potent capacities to serve the needy and the vulnerable. The one organisation that has done this so successfully is the RSS. If people with the evil and divisive motive can be committed to achieving this, then people with unitive and life-promoting intention must commit themselves more to fight against evil forces. We cannot be complacent about what we have done and what we have been doing. We need to venture into areas that would empower good people. For long, we have been attending to the wounds of societies. For once, we need to think of curbing the occurrence of wounds in societies. We need to evolve to be proactive, while continuing to be responsive to the cries of wounded humanity.

“Those who love, and who no longer view politics merely as a quest for power, “may be sure that none of our acts of love will be lost, nor any of our acts of sincere concern for others. No single act of love for God will be lost, no generous effort is meaningless, no painful endurance is wasted. All of these encircle our world like a vital force” (*Fratelli Tutti*, No. 195).

Conclusion

Pope Francis passionately and consistently makes efforts to bring alive the fruits of the Vatican II. *Fratelli Tutti* is the latest addition to that effort. The world has changed since then. The Pope has given us a hope for a new dawn, a dawn in which we all are children of the same Father and brothers and sisters of a same family. In this family, one person's cry becomes the cry of everybody. One person's joy becomes the joy of everybody else. We fall together and we rise together. With Pope Francis, I would also like finish with the prayer to the creator, seeking the spirit's presence to make true what we have read and reflected.

Lord, Father of our human family,
you created all human beings equal in dignity:
pour forth into our hearts a fraternal spirit
and inspire in us a dream of renewed encounter,
dialogue, justice and peace.

Move us to create healthier societies
and a more dignified world,
a world without hunger, poverty, violence and war.

May our hearts be open
to all the peoples and nations of the earth.
May we recognize the goodness and beauty
that you have sown in each of us,
and thus forge bonds of unity, common projects,
and shared dreams. Amen.

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